
Influence of different Pre-Sowing Treatments on Seedling Emergence of *Parkia Biglobosa*

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Abstract

Parkia biglobosa(Jacq) R.Br.ex G.Don.,the African locust bean tree belongs to the natural plant order Fabales, Family Fabaceae synonym Leguminosae and sub-family Mimosoideae. This savanna tree is vastly exploited in many parts of Nigeria for its food condiment, seasoning or spice value and for other multifarious uses. The objective of this research was to overcome dormancy usually associated with its seeds. Viable seeds determined by floatation method were subjected to pre-sowing treatments of 98% concentrated Sulphuric acid, hot water(wet heat)physical abrasion using rough sand paper for varying time durations of 20,40 and 60seconds along with treatments control. A total of 1,000 randomly picked seeds were sown in 40 perforated plastic buckets filled with loose, sieved and well drained river sand at sowing depth of 4cm based on its seed size. Each bucket diameter was 22cm with a depth of 24cm from base to the brim. The 40 buckets were arranged in a Complete Randomised Design(CRD).For each pre-sowing treatment and the treatments control/control experiment, four(4)replications of the randomly picked seeds were used with 25seeds per bucket. The study period was 35days.Data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis. Results show that 20seconds(52%) and 40seconds(49%) Sulphuric acid pre-sowing treatments were most effective with mean germination times of 9.59 and 10.30days respectively, followed by 20seconds physical scarification(41%)with mean germination time of 9days.20seconds (52%),40seconds(27%) and 60seconds(21%)wet heat treatments gave lowly germination percentages and mean germination times of 16.4, 17.1 and 16.4days respectively. Treatments control, the least gave 14% germination and mean germination time of 9.6days.Thus, 20seconds(52%)and 40seconds(49%)Sulphuric acid treatments and 20seconds(41%)physical abrasion pre- sowing treatment from eco-friendly disposition are recommended for massive propagation of *P.globosa*. Control experiment gave lowly 14% germination.

Keywords: *P.biglobosa*, Pre-sowing Treatments, Control Experiment. Germination Values.

Introduction

Parkia Robert Brown(R.Br.)genus is named after Mungo Park(1771-1806) eighteenth century Scottish medical doctor and explorer. *Parkia* trees are a genus of 40 species, belonging to Order Fabales, Family Fabaceae, synonym Leguminosae, sub-family

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Mimosoideae and are found in tropical areas of Africa, Asia and South America (Willis & Airyshaw, 1973). In Nigeria, *Parkia* genus is represented by two (2) species the near extinct forest environment- *P. bicolor* A. Chev. and predominantly savanna biome *P. biglobosa* (Jacq) R.Br ex G. Donsynonyms *P. africana* R.Br. and *P. clappertoniana* Keay. The tree reaches up to 20 metres in height and 3 metres in girth. Trunk/bole moderate with spreading branches forming a wide crown. Stem bark grey, very rough with longitudinal fissures, slashes reddish brown and exuding gum. Wood yellow and comparatively of light weight. Leaves bi-pinnately compound, rounded at the apex with a minutely hairy common stalk. *P. biglobosa* flowers December to March, flower heads are deep/blood red and highly distinctive, globose shaped and hanging in large heads at the end of long stalks. Fruiting February to July, 15 to 30 centimetres long, 3 to 4 centimetre broad, light brown in color and containing numerous brownish black seeds embedded in a yellowish, mealy, sweet tasting edible pulp. Yorubas of South western Nigeria name the plant as irugba/igi iru (Gbile and Soladoye, 2002). *P. biglobosa* is vastly exploited in many parts of Nigeria chiefly for its food condiment, seasoning or food spice value in sauce, soup and stew, the seed in particular contributes substantially to the protein, mineral elements and carbohydrate needs of the people, used as livestock feeds and in traditional medicine and for other multifarious uses (Okpala, 1990, Gill, 1992, Burkill, 1995). *P. biglobosa* alongside other savanna tree legumes such as *Dichrostachys cinerea*, *Piliostigma reticulatum*, *P. thonningii* and *Prosopis africana* play vital ecological roles in nutrient recycling and in prevention of soil erosion (Ajiboye *et.al.*, 2011).

Seed germination is the development/growth of a mature seed into a seedling with the emergence of a root forming radicle and shoot producing plumule- the realisation of viability, while seed viability is the capacity of a seed to germinate under favourable conditions (Helms, 1998).

A healthy seed that does not germinate after providing it with the necessary conditions for germination is said to be in a dormant state. Seed dormancy is the condition of a seed when it fails to germinate because of internal conditions even though external conditions of light, moisture, oxygen and temperature are favourable (Osonubi & Chukwuka, 1999). Seed dormancy may be due to a variety of reasons such as (i) seed coat restrictions based on the seeds morpho anatomical structure, (ii) physically tight pericarp (iii) chemical inhibitors within the seed (iv) embryo dormancy/rudimentary embryo (v) light sensitivity (vi) seed borne pathogens amongst others (Baskin & Baskin, 2004).

Any seed pre treatment which reduces or destroys seed coat impermeability by softening or weakening the seed coat is known as seed scarification. Seed scarification pre treatments include acid treatment, boiling (wet heat), dry heat (oven) treatment, hormonal treatments, nicking/piercing, and soaking of seeds over time amongst others are used in order to make the seed coat permeable to water and gases without destroying the seed embryo (Amen, 1968).

The aim of the experiment is to study seedling emergence percentage and seedling emergence rate of *P. biglobosa* and to break dormancy challenge usually associated with its seeds, in view of the fact that the tree is exploited presently only from the wilds, the danger of extinction is imminent, more so, there is no conscious effort at propagating *P. biglobosa*, even within its native ecological range,

Materials and Methods

Source of Seeds

Seeds of *P.biglobosa* used for this experiment were sourced from the environments of Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Seed Viability Test

The floating method of Pandey & Sinha (2010) was used to test for seed viability, the process involved dipping the randomly hand picked seeds in a beaker filled with water, floated seeds were regarded as non- viable and were discarded, while seeds that sank to the bottom of the beaker were regarded as viable and were used for the experiment.

Study Site and Management

The study was conducted at the Screen house of Plant Science and Biotechnology Department, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko (Latitude 7.4740 o N and 5.7379 o E), Ondo State, Nigeria. The study period was 35days. 1,000 seeds were sown in 40 perforated white plastic buckets filled with loose, sieved and well drained river sand. The diameter of used bucket was 22cm and depth from base to the brim was 24cm. The buckets were arranged in a complete randomised design (CRD). Four (4) replications of 100 randomly hand picked seeds 25 seeds per bucket was used for each treatment at a sowing depth of 3centimetres based on its seed size. Buckets were kept free of weeds and watering was ensured regularly throughout the 35days study period.

Seed Pre-treatments

One hundred (100) seeds set totaling 900 seeds were subjected to concentrated sulphuric acid (chemical scarification), boiled/hot water (wet heat scarification) and rough sand paper (physical abrasion /scarification) pre treatments at varying time duration of 20, 40 and 60 seconds. Also four (4) replications of one hundred (100) randomly hand picked seeds 25 seeds per bucket were sown as control experiment/treatments control.

Chemical (Sulphuric Acid) Scarification Treatment

Concentrated (98%) Sulphuric acid was poured on the seeds at varying time duration of 20, 40 and 60 seconds, the Sulphuric acid was decanted and the seeds were rinsed several times in distilled water and sown.

Boiled/hot water (Wet heat) Scarification Treatment

Boiled water at 40oCelsius was poured on the seeds, stirred for varying time duration of 20, 40 and 60 seconds and sown.

Rough Sand paper (Physical abrasion/scarification) treatment

The seeds were physically abraded with rough sand paper on all sides for varying time duration of 30, 60 and 90 seconds and sown.

Control (Untreated) Experiment/Treatments Control.

One hundred (100) un-treated seeds were sown as control experiment/treatments control.

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Germination Counts

The seeds were recorded as germinated once the plumule attains a height of 1cm above the soil surface after Ajiboye *et.al.*,2011).Record of germinated seeds were taken for the 35days study period.

Germination Percentage

Germination percentage was recorded as the ratio of seeds that germinated out of one hundred (100) sown seeds with or without treatment ,multiplied by 100.

$$\text{Germination Percentage} = \frac{\text{Total Number of Seeds That Germinated}}{\text{Total Number Of Seeds Sown}} \times 100$$

Mean Germination Time/Germination Rate

Mean Germination Time was recorded as the average of summations of the number of days for all germinated seeds.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical package for Social Science (SPSS)was used to calculate the Least Significant Difference(LSD)of the values.

Results

Table 1: Standard Error of the Pre Treatments on *Parkia Biglobosa*

Period of Treatments	Control	Acid	Wet Heat	Phy. Abrasion
0	1.35 ±0.339			
TWENTY SECS		4.99±0.492	4.28±0.750	4.02±0.501
FORTY SECS		5.05±0.536	4.49±0.790	3.44 ±0.480
SIXTY SECS		5.11 ±0.678	3.46±0.689	1.85±0.375

Figure1. Effect of pre- treatments on percentage germination of *Parkia biglobosa*

Figure2. Effect of pre- treatments on germination rate of *Parkia biglobosa*

Discussion

The breaking of seed coat dormancy using acids, hot water(wet heat),soaking, physical abrasion amongst other treatments have been demonstrated by other works (Ajiboye *et.al* 2011, Missanjo *et.al* 2014; Wen *et.al* 2024; Wen *et.al* 2024) states that the palisade layer of most leguminous seeds are composed of macro sclereid cells with secondary walls and they are impermeable to water because of the presence of hydrophobic substances such as cutin, lignin, pectin, quinones, suberin and wax. Aliero,2004 reported success effects of Sulphuric acid, physical abrasion and wet heat pre treatments of seed coat dormancy breakage on *Parkia biglobosa*.

Results show that *P.biglobosa* seeds are intolerant of the 20,40 and 60 seconds wet heat pre-treatments (21%,26% and 27% germination results)also the more the acid,the less the results(40seconds- 49% and 60seconds- 38% and best at 20seconds acid, 52% pre treatment result.) and also the more the physical abrasion pre- treatments ,also the less the result(40seconds -35% and 60seconds- 21%)implying that seed embryo is practically being drastically eroded. Control experiment gave a lowly 14% germination. Best result is 20seconds acid pre- treatment(52%)followed by 40seconds acid pre-treatment(49%),since acid has tendency of lingering in the soil environment.

Conclusion and Recommendation

A 20 second physical abrasion pre-treatment(41%),though labour intensive, it is better advocated for its eco- friendly disposition. Thus, there should be concerted efforts towards propagating this economically valuable legume tree plant for its nutritive-seasoning, medicinal and also for its other multifarious uses to prevent extinction of *P.biglobosa* tree over time.

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